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Influence Of Teachers' Effectiveness On Students' Academic Achievement In Public Schools In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Education is noted to be an effective instrument par excellence for affecting national and global development irrespective of the economic sector. It plays a veritable role in the communication process of its norms and values from one generation to another. Overabundance of studies have investigated the impact of facilities in the schools on academic achievement of the students but there seemed to be dearth of studies on influence of teachers' effectiveness on students' academic achievement in public schools. This study has its purpose to examine the influence of Teachers' Effectiveness on Students' Academic Achievement in Public Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance and the descriptive research design was used to investigate the study in which purposive random sampling procedure was adopted to sample 291 participants out of 1210 will be considered in the selected senior secondary schools from the six (6) local governments in the central comprising principals, vice principal and teachers. Two self-constructed questionnaires were used to collect data on teachers' effectiveness and students' academic achievement. After establishing their validity, reliability of the instrument, 0.89 and 0.91 were obtained respectively. Collected data were analysed using Pearson's correlation coefficient to test the stated null hypotheses. The study found that there is significant relationship existed between effectiveness and students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Sokoto state. The study recommended that government, through officials from the Ministry of Education and school principals, must ensure that schools are inspected and supervised on a regular basis in order to ensure that the teachers used method and materials effectively in the teaching and learning process in their respective schools.

Keywords: Influence, Teachers' Effectiveness, Students' Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Education is noted to be an effective instrument par excellence for affecting national and global development irrespective of the economic sector. It plays a veritable role in the communication process of its norms and values from one generation to another. Educationist and other well-meaning people have always maintained that education is the greatest legacy a nation can give to its citizens. There is therefore no better investment a nation could make than that in education, this is why one should not remain indifferent to the lapses on the educational system. The extent to which the

students, teachers and schools measure show that their educational goals have been achieved refers to academic achievement. According to Yusuf, Onifade and Bello in Isiaka, Rasaki and Pius (2021) stated that academic achievement is a measurable and observable behaviour of a student within a specific period as it consists of scores obtained by a student in a class work, test, examination and so forth. School facilities and teacher's effectiveness form one of the notable factors that are anticipated to contribute to students' academic achievement in the school system. A weighty academic achievement of students is sometimes attributed to provision and utilization of educational facilities.

According to Adeyemi (2019) there would be room for successful teaching among learners and educators if the educational training of instructors is adequately constructed. Teachers must be able to allow place for creativity, intellectualism, love, hospitality, love of wisdom, and the ability to recognize the topic of individual variations in order for good teaching to be brought to the forefront. The extent of teachers' skill, their level of adaptation, the depth of their comprehension, and many other factors must all be considered. If instruction is to be relevant and effective, the teacher must have a high degree of intelligence, skills, and knowledge in accordance with the pedagogical delivery. Furthermore, teachers must be well-versed in the things they are supposed to educate the students. Classroom evaluation, assessment of knowledge learned, and many other benefits should not be overlooked. Teachers should allow for effective classroom interaction as a way of build and evaluating the extent to which learners have learnt. Furthermore, teacher effectiveness is generally referred to in terms of the focus on students, their performance, teacher behaviors, the classroom procedures and conduct that are implemented in order to better the outcomes of the students. Teacher effectiveness besides focusing upon the performance of the students centers on the number of areas; effective teachers have to be clear about the instructional goals, possess sufficient knowledge about the content of the curriculum and the strategies for teaching, communicating appropriately with the students of what is expected of them, following appropriate teaching techniques and material to make learning useful, should be knowledgeable and aware about the students, adapting instruction to their requirements, anticipating misapprehensions in their existing knowledge, teaching students meta-cognitive strategies and providing them with opportunities to master them, addressing higher as well as lower level cognitive objectives, monitoring the understanding and performance of the students by providing feedback, integrating their instruction with that in other subject areas, and accepting responsibility for student's outcomes (Ko, Summons & Bakkum, 2013 in Adeyemi, 2019).

According to Yusuf, Onifade, and Bello (2016), academic achievement is a student's measurable and observable behavior over the course of a certain period and consists of the grades they receive on assignments, tests, and other assessments. According to Martha in Abaidoo (2018), a student's performance on an exam, test, and work activity defines their academic accomplishment. One of the significant elements thought to influence students' academic success in the educational system is the quality of the schools. Sometimes the availability and use of educational facilities is attributed to a significant portion of pupils' academic success. Wunti et al (2017) shows that students' achievements were not determined to be statistically significant in relation to the conditions of the school facilities. To these authors, what could be attributed to students' poor performance could be poor study habits, higher absenteeism from school, teachers' lack of initiative, or systemic leadership initiatives. They conclude that where working conditions are good, it results in enthusiasm, high morale, cooperation, and acceptance of responsibility. Usens (2016) in his study concluded that, teachers should make an effort to incorporate the resources offered by the school into their instructional practices in order to improve professionally and support the academic development of students. Abaidoo (2018) stated that academic success of students is defined by a student's performance in an examination, test, and in a work exercise. School facilities form one of the notable factors that are anticipated to contribute to students' academic achievement in the school system. According to Yusuf, Onifade and Bello (2016) academic achievement, is a measurable and observable behaviour of a student within a specific period as it consists of scores obtained by a student in a class work, test, examination and so forth.

Problem Statement

The student's academic progress in any subject can be related to a variety of things. When the learning environment is hospitable and suited for learning, it will discover that will be successful classroom management as well as improves students' questioning and exploration. Teachers' professional classroom management refers to the tactics and practices they employ to create healthy

teaching and learning environments. The issue of students' poor academic achievement in Nigeria has been a source of concern for all. The situation is so severe that it has resulted in a widely acknowledged drop in educational standards not only in some southern part but also in Sokoto State and Nigeria as a whole. According to Okolocha and Onyeneke (2016) available statistics from various secondary schools visited revealed that students who sat for exams received credit or above in either business or native languages, while the rest were either pass, failed, or result. In addition, fieldwork conducted in selected secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria, on the results of the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), revealed that poor performance of students in English, mathematics, physics and chemistry. However, teacher's attitude has a substantial impact on student attention in the classroom. This is what calls the interest of the researcher to conduct this research to examine the school facilities and teacher effectiveness on students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to examine the relationship between:

1. Teacher mastery of subject and Student's Academic Achievement in public secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria.
2. Teacher classroom evaluation and Student's Academic Achievement in public secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study tries to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent teachers' mastery subject correlates with students' academic achievement in Public secondary schools in Sokoto state?
2. To what extent teachers' classroom evaluation correlates with students' academic achievement in Public secondary schools in Sokoto state?

Research Hypotheses

The following research null hypotheses were formulated to test the relationship between the two variables of the study:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of subject and students' academic achievement in public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' classroom evaluation and students' academic achievement in public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Teachers Mastery of Subject and Students' Academic Achievement

Keith (2016) express that it is obvious that, if you are going to teach a subject, then you should really know a lot about the subject, certainly in secondary schools, where teachers often specialise into one or two subject areas, there is a real emphasis on the teacher's knowledge of the subject matter. Teacher competence needs to be very high in order for meaningful teaching-learning to take place. Being taught by an effective teacher has important consequences on student academic achievement. Teachers matter more to student achievement than any other aspect of schooling. According to Lydiah, Nelly and Ruth, (2014), it is of necessity that teachers master the subject matter before imparting it to learners since it enables the teacher to adequately prepare for content delivery. The mastery of subject matter is the foundation upon which the education of a teacher is based. The teacher requires among other things the skill of mastering the subject matter and being able to establish the interrelationships between different subjects. These are essential for the professional preparation of a teacher and anchor firmly on a foundation of general education of a teacher which contributes to the growth of a teacher as a person. A meta-analysis of current research on the impact of a quality teacher on student achievement by the Centre for Public Education as cited in Jaime (2008), defined dimensions of teacher quality such as content knowledge, teaching experience, professional certification.

According to Keith (2016) a meta-analysis of more than 1000 educational studies was conducted by Hattie who identified 138 different factors that influenced student learning. The required effect size for a student to make a year's progress was 0.4. According to Hattie, teacher subject-matter knowledge had an effect size of 0.19, meaning that it was far less

effective than other factors like classroom management (0.52) or effective teacher feedback (0.75).

Teacher Classroom Evaluation and Students' Academic Achievement

Johnson (2017) focused on the potential relationship between the effectiveness of teachers and student growth in California upper basic school. The study was facilitated in response to the TEACHNJ Act, which mandated that teacher tenure would, at least in part, be determined by the teachers' evaluation ratings, in an effort to improve the level of teaching and, in turn, enhance student growth as a result. The quantitative analysis involved several variables, including many at the school level, the teacher level, and characteristics of the students. One of the predominant questions at the core of this study was identifying how student growth might or might not be influenced by a teacher's effectiveness, as represented by their practice score or evaluation rating. The researcher sample of participants were all relative to New Jersey; the teachers participating were employed to teach Grades 4 through 7 in either language arts (N = 149) or mathematics (N = 145) from thirty participating schools. Ordinal regression was then utilized as the analytic method for examining the possible relationship between teacher characteristics and student growth, ultimately determining that a positively correlated relationship existed. The researcher found that as teacher ratings increased, so did student growth, regardless of the urban setting and ethnic composition of the student sample.

Alexander (2016) focused on teachers and students within the state of Illinois. This study also examined standardized test outcomes, regarding math and reading, specifically, which is similar to the study presented in this paper. However, distinct from this study utilized the measures of Academic Progress as the instrument, which measured student outcomes. Final participant sample was derived from seven elementary schools, but featured only fifth-grade students (N = 317) and teachers employed at the same grade level (N = 19) for the 2015–2016 academic year. A correlation analysis was then implemented for testing the potential relationship between teacher evaluation ratings and student math and reading test performance, respectively. As a result, the researcher reported no statistically significant relationships between any of the variables tested (Alexander, 2016). Perhaps even more interesting was that examining the correlation outcomes more closely, negative correlations were realized in each case with a Pearson's r of $-.074$ ($p = .188$) and $-.103$ ($p = .069$) for math and reading, respectively. Therefore, although the subsequent relationships were not significant, as teacher effectiveness improved, as measured by evaluation ratings, student performance actually worsened. These outcomes persisted, even in spite of the fact that the study attempted to control for potential confounding variables by excluding students with excessive absences or those who were included in special education, as indicated by an individualized educational plan.

In another research endeavor, Medlock (2017) focused on a high-performing state regarding student standardized testing outcomes in order to examine a potential underlying causation for the ethnic variation that persisted. More specifically, an achievement gap existed between Caucasian students and their African-American counterparts within the state of North Carolina. In this instance, the standardized test used as the instrument of measurement was the state end-of-grade test on mathematics for 8th grade students for the 2014–2015 and 2015–2016 academic years. Ultimately, the mixed methods analysis revealed that teacher evaluation ratings were not a predominant indicator of student achievement nor were student characteristics responsible for the distinct gap between students of different ethnic backgrounds. Instead, after quantitative methods combined with qualitative interviews were analyzed, it was found that teachers' lack of interest in understanding cultural factors may prove influential, as well as differing learning styles, that were the primary drivers behind the gap that continued to plague an otherwise high performing district.

Kraft et al. (2020) in their article titled Existing evidence on the effects of evaluation reforms their study using a similar identification strategy found that state-level evaluation reforms raised the quality of new teachers but also decreased their job satisfaction and lowered the overall supply of newly licensed teacher candidates. Johnson (2017) focused on the potential relationship between the effectiveness of teachers and student growth. The study was facilitated in response to the Teachn Act, which mandated that teacher tenure would, at least in part, be determined by the teachers' evaluation ratings, in an effort to improve the level of teaching and, in turn, enhance student growth as a result. The quantitative analysis involved several variables, including many at the school level, the teacher

level, and characteristics of the students. One of the predominant questions at the core of this study was identifying how student growth might or might not be influenced by a teacher’s effectiveness, as represented by their practice score or evaluation rating.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive survey of the correlational research type in order to collect data on influence of teachers’ effectiveness on students’ academic achievement in public schools in Sokoto state, and quantitative approach was used because the data analysis technique was statistical in purpose to test the hypotheses that have been set. The study target population included school administrators (principals and Vice Principals) and teachers from which the data necessary for the completion of this research was obtained with the sample of 291 participants out of 1210 were purposively selected in the selected Public Senior Secondary Schools from the twenty five (25) public Senior Secondary Schools within the Sokoto South Educational Zone. Self-constructed constructed questionnaire titled: Teacher Job Effectiveness Rating Scale (TJERS) based on five (5) points rating agreement; 5 points = strongly agreed, 4 points = agreed, 3 points = Neutral, 2 points =Disagree, 1 point = strongly disagreed will be used to obtain information need for this research. Validity and the reliability of the questionnaire were examined by computing Content Validity Index (CVI) and the 0.89 and 0.91 were obtained respectively. Responses to the questionnaire items (quantitative data) were used to analyze the research questions of the study. Specifically, descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) was used. Pearson Product moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study to highlight the level of relationship exist between teacher effectiveness and students’ academic achievement in public secondary school in Sokoto state.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent teachers’ mastery of subject correlates with students’ academic achievement in Public secondary schools in Sokoto state?*

Table 1: Teachers’ Mastery of subject as correlates with students’ academic achievement

S/No.	Item Statement	Agreed	%	Disagree	%
1.	I like to see that they explain every concept after each lesson	68	59.9	52	40.1
2.	I want to become perfect in writing about things I for students to learn	62	50.7	62	49.3
3.	I want be able to build on more ideas from which I taught students to learn	65	57.4	55	42.6
4.	I like to make the students express themselves in the public	66	58.9	54	41.1
5.	I want the students to become perfect in calculations	64	55.1	56	44.9
Percentage aggregate		56.4%		43.6%	

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 1 showed that percentage aggregate of 56.4% of the respondents totally agreed that among their mastery of subject which is related to their students’ academic achievement towards learning are: to see that the students can explain every concept after each lesson, want to become perfect in writing about things they learn, want be able to build on more ideas from which they have learn, like to express theirs selves in the public and to become perfect in calculations, while 43.6% aggregate percentage disagree with the statements. This indicated that majority of the respondents were all agreed that teacher mastery of subject is correlated with students’ academic achievement in learning in public secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Question 2: *To what extent teachers' classroom evaluation correlates with students' academic achievement in Public secondary schools in Sokoto state?*

Table 2: Teachers' Classroom Evaluation as Correlates with Students' Academic Achievement

S/No.	Item Statement	Agreed	%	Disagree	%
1.	I like to engaged in a group assignments	64	55.1	56	44.9
2.	Group discussion is one of my best learning method	58	49.3	62	50.7
3.	Presentations during lesson is very important	65	57.4	55	42.6
4.	I like informal discussions with my teachers	68	59.9	52	40.1
5.	Excursion is one of my best learning activities	64	55.1	56	44.9
Percentage aggregate		55.36%		44.64%	

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 2 shows that percentage aggregate of 55.36% of the respondents totally agreed that among their learning participation and which also improve their academic achievement are: to engaged in a group assignments, group discussion is one of their best learning method, presentations during lesson is very important, they like informal discussions with their teachers and Excursion is one of my best learning activities, while 44.64% aggregate percentage disagree with the statements. This indicated that majority of the students were all agreed that students' learning participation in the table of students in secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.

PRESENTATION OF DATA OF RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Research Hypotheses 1:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' mastery of subject and students' academic achievement in public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between Teachers' Mastery of Subject and Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria

Variable	N	\bar{x}	Df	Sig-Value	P-Value	Decision
Teacher Mastery of Subject	219	1.0	0.05	0.00	0.58	H ₀ Rejected
Academic Achievement	219	0.00				

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 3 shows that at 0.05 level of accuracy, the computed sig-value and P-value are 0.58 and 0.00 respectively. Since the computed P-value is greater than the tabulated value, thus the hypothesis was rejected. Thus there is relationship between teacher mastery of subject and students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Hypotheses 2:

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' classroom evaluation and students' academic achievement in public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Relationship between Teachers' Classroom Evaluation and Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Sokoto State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	Df	Sig-Value	P-Value	Decision
Teacher classroom evaluation	219	1.0	0.05	0.00	.545	H ₀ Rejected
Academic Achievement	219	0.00				

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 4 show that at 0.05 level of accuracy, the computed sig-value and P-value are 0.00 and .545 respectively, since the computed P-value is greater than the tabulated value, the hypothesis was rejected. Thus there is relationship between teacher classroom evaluation and Students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Sokoto state.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the research questions answered and analyzed, the study discusses the result of the findings as follows:

1. The findings from the research question one show that percentage aggregate of 56.4% of the respondents totally agreed that among their mastery of subject which is related to their students' academic achievement towards learning are: to see that the students can explain every concept after each lesson, want to become perfect in writing about things they learn, want be able to build on more ideas from which they have learn, like to express theirs selves in the public and to become perfect in calculations, while 43.6% aggregate percentage disagree with the statements. The finding from the research hypotheses one highlighted that there is significant relationship between teacher mastery of subject and student academic achievement and the null hypotheses was rejected.
2. The findings from the research question two show that percentage aggregate of 55.36% of the respondents totally agreed that among their learning participation and which also improve their academic achievement are: to engaged in a group assignments, group discussion is one of their best learning method, presentations during lesson is very important, they like informal discussions with their teachers and Excursion is one of my best learning activities, while 44.64% aggregate percentage disagree with the statements. The finding from the research hypotheses two highlighted that there is significant relationship between teacher classroom evaluation and student academic achievement and the null hypotheses was rejected.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That there is effective influence of teacher effectiveness and students' academic achievement in which significant relationship exist between the teacher mastery of subject and students' academic achievement in the public secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.
2. That there is effective influence of teacher effectiveness and students' academic achievement in which significant relationship exist between the teacher classroom evaluation and students' academic achievement in public secondary school in Sokoto metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are provided:

1. The principals should always ensure that they always supervised the teaching and learning activities in their school for proper use of method of teaching and effective teaching and learning in the schools.
2. Training and retraining of staff concerning school management should be organized by the state ministry of education for the subordinate to acquire more skills concerning school administrative effectiveness.

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